

Dynamics of high-density unipolar epicardial electrograms during Pulsed Field Ablation (PFA)

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

Pulsed field ablation (PFA) is a novel non-thermal cardiac ablation technology based on irreversible electroporation (IRE). While areas of IRE lead to durable lesions, the surrounding regions, where reversible electroporation (RE) occurs, recover. The behavior of local electrograms in areas of different electroporation levels remains unknown. The goal of this study is to characterize electrogram dynamics after PFA in IRE and RE areas.

METHODS:

A total of 6 domestic swine were used. PFA was applied in the epicardium of the right and left ventricles using a focal monopolar catheter. Additional radiofrequency ablations (RFA) were performed. Epicardial unipolar electrograms were acquired at baseline and for 60 min post PFA/RFA using a high-density electrode matrix attached to the epicardium. Electrogram dynamics were analyzed in areas corresponding to different levels of electroporation. Acute lesion formation was assessed after 3-5 hours by TTC staining.

RESULTS:

Electrogram analysis demonstrated a clear association between electrogram changes and the level of electroporation. Immediately after PFA, electrograms displayed : a significant decrease in R/S wave amplitude; a large elevation of the ST segment and; a large decrease in their $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$. Marked changes in electrograms were observed beyond the lesion area. Thereafter, a gradual recovery was observed. The evolution of all the electrogram parameters throughout the 60 min after PFA was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) between the IRE and RE areas. Acute lesion staining showed significantly larger depth for PFA lesions compared to RFA.

CONCLUSIONS:

This study shows that unipolar electrograms can differentiate between RE and IRE areas during the first 30 min post ablation. Differences after the first 30 min are less evident. Our findings could result useful for immediate lesion assessment after PFA and warrant further investigation.

Nonstandard Abbreviations and Acronyms

PFA Pulsed Field Ablation

RFA Radiofrequency Ablation

RE Reversible Electroporation

IRE Irreversible Electroporation

ELF Electric Field

EGM Electrogram

Introduction

The use of irreversible electroporation (IRE) as a non-thermal method for ablation of cardiac arrhythmias, also known as Pulsed Field Ablation (PFA), has rapidly moved from preclinical studies to clinical application in recent years¹⁻⁴. Despite the apparent good results of the initial use of the technique, many of the mechanisms that drive chronic lesion formation remain poorly understood.

The phenomenon of electroporation consists in the transient increase in cell membrane permeability to molecular species upon the application of a short and intense electric field (ELF). If the exposure parameters are below certain levels, the cell membrane recovers back to its pre-exposure state and cells survive, this is known as Reversible Electroporation (RE). On the contrary, if the exposure levels are above a certain threshold, cell death is induced as a consequence of electroporation, which is known as Irreversible Electroporation (IRE). One of the main challenges in the PFA field deals with the transient effects that are produced in the reversible electroporation areas. Acute lesion formation during cardiac ablation with thermal techniques (Radiofrequency) is usually assessed by recording the local electrical activity changes in the tissue. However, recent studies have shown how the attenuation or even complete absence of cardiac electrograms in the area treated by PFA immediately after application, is not directly linked to chronic tissue lesion formation⁵⁻⁹. This so-called “stunning effect” is attributed to reversible electroporation in which cardiomyocytes are transiently disrupted but the ELF magnitude in that area was not enough to cause permanent cell death. This means that the size of the acutely affected area is larger than the final resulting lesion. This effect has important consequences in the clinical practice as it has been shown that, despite acute vein isolation is observed in nearly 100 % of cases, this may not be directly translated into long-term efficacy¹⁰. Consequently, understanding the differences in electrogram changes and recovery process after PFA application between irreversible and reversible electroporation areas should be of particular interest from a clinical perspective.

The goal of this study was to characterize the dynamic changes in the local electrical activity of the ventricular epicardium before and up to an hour after PFA at different voltages (1000V and 2000V) and to evaluate if there are electrical differences that allow to distinguish permanent from transient damage. For that purpose, we registered the unipolar electrograms using a high-density electrode matrix positioned around the energy application point. Additionally, radiofrequency ablation was also used for comparison.

Methods

The data and analysis methods that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Study population

This study involved 6 domestic swine (Landrace-Large White cross) weighing 57 ± 8 kg. The animals were premedicated with midazolam (0.6 mg/kg) and ketamine (12 mg/kg) intramuscularly. General anesthesia was induced with intravenous propofol (2–4 mg/kg) and was maintained with a mixture of oxygen and sevoflurane inhalation (2.5%–3.5%). After endotracheal intubation, animals were mechanically ventilated. Analgesia was maintained during the entire procedure with an intravenous fentanyl infusion (0.1 μ g/kg/min). The surface ECG was continuously recorded using a CardioSoft system (GE Healthcare, Germany). The study protocol was approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee of our institution, and fully conformed the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals, 8th ed. (National Research Council. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press, 2010).

Experimental procedures

A median sternotomy was performed, and the pericardium was opened to expose the heart in a pericardial cradle. Once the surface of the ventricles was exposed, we selected one site in the left ventricle (LV) and one site in the right ventricle (RV) and placed a high-density electrode matrix (see details below) on each site. A 3D-printed positioning frame sutured at the epicardium was used as a support for the PFA applications and to stabilize the electrode matrix (see Fig. 1a), in such a way that the point that was subjected to the greatest electric field corresponds to the center of the matrix (all ventricular sites were free of epicardial fat). Once the recordings were finished, two new locations sufficiently separated from the previous ablation points were selected and the procedure was repeated again. At least 3 hours after the last ablation point was performed, animals were euthanized by inducing ventricular fibrillation and cardiac tissue was immediately harvested for analysis.

Epicardial mapping of ventricular electrograms

Epicardial mapping of unipolar electrograms was performed in the epicardial surfaces of the left and right ventricles simultaneously using two patches of 128 microelectrodes each (square area of 9 x 9.5 mm), with an interelectrode space of 0.75 mm. Both patches were connected to a BioSemi acquisition system (Biosemi, The Netherlands). All recordings were performed at a sampling rate of 2 kHz and the reference electrode was placed at the upper mediastinal region close to the border of the sternotomy. The measurement protocol consisted in a 1-minute baseline recording, followed by the removal of both electrodes patches to perform the epicardial PFA lesions. Immediately after the ablations (\approx 1 min) the electrodes patches were repositioned in each ventricle to perform a continuous post ablation recording during 60 minutes in all animals. In at least one site of each animal we repositioned the recording patches 180 min after the ablation and performed an additional 1-minute recording.

To confirm that the changes observed were not affected by the removal and repositioning of the electrode patches we performed a sham measurement in two animals that consisted in a baseline recording followed by the removal of both electrode patches, the placement of the catheter in the epicardium for 20 seconds (without applying PFA) and then we repositioned both electrode patches in each ventricle to perform a continuous post ablation recording for 60 minutes.

Pulsed Field Ablation lesions

A custom built generator (EPULSUS®-FBML1–5, Energy Pulse Systems, Lisbon, Portugal) capable of producing microsecond range, biphasic pulses was used to deliver the PFA treatments. The waveform used was validated in a previous study in small animals¹¹. Namely, it consisted in a sequence 10 biphasic bursts with 100 μ s duration for each burst. The bursts were delivered with a one second delay between them (i.e. 10 s total treatment duration per point). Each burst consisted in a group of square biphasic pulses of 5.55 μ s duration per polarity and a delay between each change in polarity of 300 ns (internal burst frequency of approximately 90 kHz). Two different PFA groups were studied corresponding to two different applied voltage levels: 1000 V and 2000

V (values are peak voltages). Voltage and current were monitored during PFA applications using a digital oscilloscope (Rohde & Schwarz RTB2004), and current probe (Tektronix TCP2020).

PFA was delivered unsynchronised from the ECG in a monopolar way between a focal electrode positioned in contact with the epicardium through the plastic holder previously described and a return patch attached to the back of the animal. Conductive electrocardiography gel was used to ensure good electrical contact. The focal electrode consisted in an 8F 4 mm tip ablation catheter (Thermocool® Smartouch®, Biosense Webster).

Radiofrequency ablation lesions

In order to improve the understanding of our results and provide a fair comparison with the conventional ablation technique (radiofrequency), we performed an additional set of non-irrigated radiofrequency lesions. Radiofrequency was delivered in a power-control mode using a Stockert 70 RF generator (Biosense Webster, Inc.) and the same focal electrode previously described. Because swine are especially prone to develop VF after RF delivery we paced the heart at 180 bpm during each RF application. We created the RF lesions with a contact force of 10-14g using a power-control mode of 30 W for 30 seconds.

Tissue processing

In order to assess the extent of acute lesion formation, we used triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (TTC) staining. TTC staining provides information about the metabolic activity of the tissue. To allow recovery of the areas of RE and ensure lesion formation in the areas of IRE we decided to wait between 3 and 5 hours from the last PFA application to euthanasia in order to leave lesions enough time to correctly develop⁸. Once harvested, and because the ablation points were easily visually identifiable, small pieces of ventricular tissue corresponding to the lesion points were collected, cut in two halves and immersed in a 1 % TTC solution prepared in PBS for 30 min at 37 °C. Subsequently, tissue images were acquired and analysed using open-source software QuPath to estimate maximum lesion width and depth.

Signal processing and data analysis

An offline analysis of the unipolar electrograms was done with custom-made Matlab scripts (MathWorks, USA) and the following parameters were analyzed in 1 minute intervals during the whole recording: RS amplitude (in mV): defined as the sum of the absolute values of R and S-wave amplitudes; the maximum negative slope of the RS complex $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ (in mV/s), the ST-segment deviation from the J point (in mV) (More details in Supplementary Information A5). The signals were high-pass filtered (cutoff frequency 0.16 Hz) and low-pass filtered (cutoff frequency 100 Hz). As the goal of this work was to study the evolution of local electrograms in areas exposed to different ELF magnitudes (corresponding to different levels of electroporation), we analyzed subsets of microelectrodes grouped in circumferences centered around the ablation point. Fig.1b and 1c illustrate how, for the monopolar configuration used, the ELF radially distributes in the tissue, and how the different circumferences (rings) correspond to a different ELF magnitude.

Center of the lesion was manually established during the offline analysis to correct possible movement artifacts because the core of the lesion did not always coincide with the center of the recording matrix. Center of the lesion was assigned to the circular region where maximum changes in the electrogram morphology were observed through the whole matrix (see examples provided in Supplementary Information A1). Subsequently, microelectrodes were grouped in rings of different diameters around the center of the lesion. The diameters of these rings were fixed for all conditions (see Fig. 2c).

For each ablation voltage condition, final analysis was performed in three rings corresponding to: i) the center of the lesion; ii) lesion border and iii) lesion periphery. The ring corresponding to each of these regions was assigned based on the correspondence between measured lesion width (or lesion diameter) of the TTC stained samples and diameters of the available rings. Central ring was always the first ring around the center of the lesion (diameter=2.65 mm). Lesion border was assigned to the ring closest to the internal border of the lesion (inside the lesion). Finally, lesion periphery was the ring closest to the external border of the lesion (outside the lesion). Please, refer to Fig. 2c for more details.

Statistical analysis

Continuous data were expressed as mean and standard deviation (SD). Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare temporal changes in R and S-waves amplitudes, $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ values and ST-segment of the electrograms from baseline to the selected post-ablation intervals. Comparisons of the same electrogram measurements between regions (lesion center, lesion border and lesion periphery) were made using an analysis of variance or Kruskal–Wallis test, as appropriate. Post-hoc analysis for pairwise comparisons were made using a Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney test. Significance was defined as a two-tailed $p < 0.05$ and was adjusted for multiple comparison by Bonferroni correction. Analyses were performed with IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0.

**** Figure 1 here****

Results

A total of n=20 ablation points were included in the analysis (total individual electrograms analyzed in the left ventricle: n=119 at 1000 V and n=79 at 2000 V). Direct visualization of epicardium before staining revealed no signs of thermal damage. Temperature recordings performed during PFA at the application point showed no temperatures over 55°C, (see Supplementary Information A3 for more details). We systematically observed partial tissue discoloration in a circular region at the lesion points. The pale colored regions were clearly visible even several hours after PFA treatment. For the highest dose applied, a central area of hemorrhage was systematically observed compatible with previous studies describing capillary endothelium disruption and erythrocyte extravasation ¹².

Although applications were not synchronized with the cardiac cycle, no ventricular fibrillation was induced in any of the applications.

Lesion assessment

The gross pathology of the focal ablations performed displayed well demarcated TTC-negative areas with semi ellipsoidal shape. Figure 2a displays the acute lesion dimensions obtained after TTC staining for the two PFA doses studied (1000 and 2000 V). In Figure 2b a representative example of a central cut of two TTC-stained lesions is shown. Measured lesion depth was significantly different between 1000 V and 2000 V (5.1 ± 0.9 mm vs. 8.2 ± 1.1 mm, $p<0.01$). Similarly, significant differences were obtained for lesion width between 1000 V and 2000 V (6.6 ± 1.2 mm vs. 9.3 ± 0.8 mm, $p<0.01$). Mean lesion depth increased by 62 % from 1000 V to 2000 V while lesion width increased 39 %.

Based on this lesion assessment, we established the dimension of the area of IRE, for the two voltages studied. Figure 2c shows an overlay of the electrodes matrix, the rings used in the electrogram analysis and the lesion areas for 1000 V (red) and 2000 V (blue). For 1000 V, central ring corresponds to lesion to center, ring 2 to lesion border and ring 3 to lesion periphery. For

2000 V, central ring was also assigned to lesion center, ring 4 is in the lesion border and ring 5 corresponds to lesion periphery.

**** Figure 2 here****

Epicardial mapping

Acute morphological changes of local electrograms

At baseline, the unipolar electrograms showed a R/S complex, with a sharp QRS complex characterized by a large $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ followed by isoelectric ST-segment and positive or negative T-wave. The morphology of the electrograms was uniform in the whole area recorded by the electrodes matrix ($p > 0.05$ for all baseline regional comparisons). Figure 3a and Figure 4a show an illustrative example of the morphological changes in the epicardial electrograms of the left ventricle after performing PFA at 1000 V and 2000 V, respectively (similar results for the right ventricle are provided in Supplementary Information A2). In Supplementary videos V1 and V2, the complete evolution of electrograms in the 60 min recording period is shown for 1000 V and 2000 V, respectively.

In both voltage conditions, the greatest morphological changes are recorded in the first 1-2 minutes after PFA, characterized by: a) significant decrease in R/S wave amplitude; b) a large elevation of the ST segment leading to monophasic potentials and; c) a large decrease in their $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ (Fig 3a and 4a). At 1000 V, the changes were significantly more pronounced in the

central region around the catheter application site (p values < 0.05 compared to the other regions), whereas for 2000 V, all electrograms were strongly modified with no regional differences observed ($p > 0.05$).

Short-term evolution of local electrograms

During the time interval from 2 to 60 minutes after the PFA there was a dynamic recovery of the electrograms in both voltage conditions. This recovery was characterized by a decrease in the ST segment elevation, reaching values similar to baseline at the end, and an increase in both the values of the R/S waves and in $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$, remaining significantly lower than baseline at the end of the 60 min observation period ($p < 0.01$ for all regions and conditions) (Fig. 3b and 4b). As shown, the magnitude of the changes and the dynamics of recovery depends on the magnitude of the ELF to which a particular region was exposed: greater changes and more persistent for the center ring compared to border and periphery.

Quantification of the dynamic evolution of the ST-segment, R/S waves and $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ is summarized for the three different regions (center, border and periphery) for 1000 V and 2000 V, in Table 1. The differences between the center area (IRE) and periphery (RE) remained significant ($p < 0.05$) throughout the 60 min recording period for all electrogram parameters.

When comparing the border with periphery, each parameter displayed a different behavior. The ST-segment elevation showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) from 20 min to 60 min for 1000 V and between 10 min to 35 min at 2000 V. The R/S showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for the first 19 minutes for 1000V and between 12 to 22 min for 2000V, and then level off for the rest of the recording time.

The evolution of $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ displayed a more complex behavior. At the lesion periphery $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ displayed a very fast recovery only during the first 5 minutes and then stabilized for the remaining observation period. For the 1000 V condition, the center and the border had similar values throughout the recording; while the periphery showed significant differences with the border during all the recording time ($p < 0.05$). For 2000 V, there were differences between center

and border up to 35min ($p < 0.05$), but border and periphery did not show statistically significant differences.

**** Figure 3 here****

**** Figure 4 here****

**** Table 1 here *****

EGM-derived cutoff values

In order to determine the myocardial areas of RE and IRE we calculated the cutoff values for each study variable using as threshold the data corresponding to the border region. For RS amplitude and $|dV/dt|_{\max}$ values are provided as percentages of reduction vs. their baseline values. For the ST-segment elevation variable the calculation was performed as the percentage of recovery with respect to the maximum change observed immediately after PFA application (1 min recording). Cutoff values are provided in Table 2 both for 1000 V and 2000 V. See how the cutoffs values are very similar for both voltage conditions. For instance, we could predict that 5 minutes after

the PFA application a site in the myocardium showing a unipolar EGM with a RS amplitude reduction greater than 61.8 % vs baseline will be in an irreversibly electroporated area. Or 15 min after PFA, an area displaying a recovery of the maximum ST-segment elevation greater than 61.9 % will be a RE area.

**** Table 2 here ****

Subacute changes in local electrograms

In two lesions, an electrogram recording was performed 180 min after treatment. We observed: a) complete normalization of the ST-segment in all electrodes at 1000 V and 2000 V; b) the RS amplitude values remained stable between 60 and 180 min for all regions and voltage conditions and c) compared to their respective values at 60 min, $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ values remained almost unchanged. Only at 1000 V there was a slight decrease in the central ring and an increase in the lesion periphery ring. Refer to Supplementary Table I for a summary of the results.

Comparison with RF ablation

As a shown in Fig. 5a the lesion width obtained with RFA was very similar to PFA at 2000 V while lesion depth was significantly different. The similarity in lesion width allowed us to analyze electrograms at the same rings as the ones used in the analysis at PFA 2000 V, i.e., same distance from application point in both conditions.

The electrogram changes after RFA are clearly different from the changes observed after PFA (Fig 5b). The ST-segment increase during the first minutes after the ablation is less pronounced and displays a slower behavior, also, the first recovery phase is slower than in PFA. In addition, the increase in the ST-segment detected in the lesion periphery is almost negligible, while for PFA at 2000 V there is massive increase in the periphery.

Similarly, the changes quantified in the $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ during RFA at the lesion periphery are smaller and display a very rapid recovery to baseline levels. On the contrary, at the lesion center there is an abrupt decrease that does not evolve over time.

**** Figure 5 here****

Discussion

Main findings

This study shows, for the first time, that the dynamics of high-density unipolar epicardial electrograms differ between RE and IRE areas after PFA application. Although important changes in the unipolar electrograms are detected beyond the irreversible electroporation area, our results show how it is possible to acutely differentiate between the areas that will result in a durable lesion from those that will recover within the first 30 min after ablation.

Additionally, we show that monopolar epicardial applications of PFA produce significantly deeper lesions than RFA in the same setting.

Transient electrical changes

This study shows how the acute changes in the electrograms of cardiac tissue and the dynamics of recovery produced after PFA are highly dependent on the ELF exposure magnitude and affect regions of tissue beyond the lesion area. This effect is inherent to all PFA systems because the resulting ELF distribution created by any catheter used in PFA is highly non-uniform and will create areas of tissue exposed to lower ELF magnitudes where RE will occur. The transient increase of membrane permeability to molecules produced by RE can greatly modify the balance of ions between the intracellular and extracellular spaces modifying the electrical activity of cardiomyocytes. However, little is known about this transient process and whether the characteristics of these changes significantly differ in magnitude or dynamics from the changes observed in the irreversibly damaged area enabling a clear distinction between the durable and non-durable PFA effects.

Our results show how the different parameters of the electrograms analyzed dynamically recover after PFA and suggest different dynamics between the RE and IRE areas.

First, regarding the changes observed in the ST-segment elevation, our results show how this parameter can be used to identify RE and IRE areas in the first 30 min after ablation. This would be very useful for current PVI procedures with single shot devices where dwell time in the left atrium is short. However, as the delay between ablation and tissue assessment is extended, the differences between RE and IRE are much less evident, limiting the use of this parameter alone for identification of RE areas. This is clearly illustrated in the changes over time observed in the cutoffs values calculated for this parameter (refer to Table 2). It is interesting to highlight how similar are the values for 1000 and 2000 V. Transient ST-segment elevation has been reported in some clinical studies^{13,14}, but is not generally observed during PFA procedures. The most plausible explanation for the observed ST-segment elevation in PFA is the massive potassium release to the extracellular medium caused by the permeabilization of the cell membrane by electroporation (reversible or irreversible). According to other studies, transient ST-segment elevation and potassium concentration are directly related¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The transient recovery observed could be explained by the gradual washout of extracellular potassium from the extracellular space, leading to normalization of the ST segment.

The other two electrogram parameters analyzed, the RS amplitude and the $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$, are both accepted as changes compatible with local lesion formation¹⁸⁻²¹ in radiofrequency ablation. In our study, we observe how these parameters also change beyond the lesion area. The cutoff values calculated for these two parameters, which are very similar between 1000 V and 2000 V, can provide a good estimate for determining RE or IRE regions at specific time points. As shown in the color maps of Figs 3c and 4c, a careful selection of level thresholds provides a fair estimate of the lesion area. Interestingly, the recovery dynamics during the first 5 min are completely different between areas of RE (very fast recovery) and IRE (very slow recovery). These different dynamics could also enable to differentiate between both regions.

Our analysis systematically observed significant differences between the center of the lesion and the lesion periphery in all parameters and conditions. However, differences between the border and periphery were only detectable at specific time intervals that strongly varied depending on

the condition analyzed. This suggests that although it is possible to identify clear differences between the area of major effect and the non-affected area, it could be challenging to define the border of the lesion.

Finally, our results show how some recovery processes stabilize a few minutes post PFA while others develop until the end of the 60 min recording period. Furthermore, the subacute observations performed reveal non-significant differences between the values at 60 min and 180 min. Thus, it seems reasonable to suggest that a 60 min waiting period would provide reliable information about PFA efficacy.

Differences with Radiofrequency ablation

We observed different dynamics in electrogram changes after RFA compared to PFA. Our measurements demonstrate how for RFA the electrical changes in the tissue that is not thermally damaged are negligible while the changes observed inside the lesion area are consistent and display only a minimal transient behavior that stabilizes at 30 min. This demonstrates that, after this period, the information provided by the electrograms in RFA can clearly reflect the treatment outcome. On the contrary, for PFA important transient effects are observed inside and outside the lesion making it difficult to define the lesion area. The partial recovery observed inside the lesion area for PFA is likely linked to the far field effects due to the unipolar recording strategy and the impact of reversible electroporation processes in the surrounding tissue.

Lesion morphology

Finally, regarding lesion morphology, for PFA we obtained remarkably elongated lesions (width/depth ratios between 1.3 and 1.1 for 1000 V for 2000 V, respectively). Our results are in accordance to previous observations²² and demonstrate clear differences with the lesion shape obtained by RFA where width/depth ratios can vary between 1.7 and 2.3 depending on the energy application strategy²³. In the comparison with RFA performed in this study, lesions displayed a width/depth ratio of 2.3. The elongated lesion shape obtained with PFA and a monopolar electrode suggest that PFA would be advantageous for deep targets compared to RFA. However, the

elongated shape seems to differ from the expected ELF distribution predicted by relatively simplified computational models ^{4,24} and opens the door to increase the complexity in modelling to understand and accurately reproduce the observations.

Study limitations

In this study, PFA was applied epicardially in an open chest model, which it is not the preferred approach in clinical practice. However, this methodology allowed a perfect control of the position and contact of the catheter and electrogram recording electrodes matrix.

We cannot ensure a perfect correlation between the behavior in epicardial and endocardial ventricular electrograms. Additionally, our results could also differ if performed in atrial tissue, epi or endocardially. Thus, these findings are limited to the delivery catheter, PFA generator and the electrodes used to measure signals and may not reflect the behavior across clinical catheter tips and generators. The cutoff values reported in the results section should be taken with caution. However, due to the good reproducibility of these values between 1000V and 2000V encourage to consider this as a first approximation/proof of concept to construct an algorithm in the current cardiac mapping systems to allow a rapid evaluation of the effectiveness of PFA lesions.

Compared to high density mapping catheters, where minimum interelectrode separation is between 2 and 3 mm, the interelectrode separation of the patch used in this study is 0.75 mm. Then, we could expect that for a static situation, high density mapping catheters will have a lower spatial resolution than the system used in the present study. However, as these catheters are designed to be displaced inside the cardiac chamber, spatial resolution will increase by overlapping measurements acquired at different positions.

It is important to mention that the biphasic waveform used in this study was optimized for creating deep ventricular lesions and avoid thermal damage but on the other hand, it induced important muscle contractions during applications. From a clinical perspective, the level of muscle contractions observed would require the use of general anesthesia and neuromuscular blockade. As previously shown ¹¹, waveform could be optimized to reduce muscle contractions.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that the changes and recovery dynamics in the unipolar local epicardial electrograms after PFA are different between the reversible and irreversible electroporation areas. Unipolar EGMs can acutely differentiate IRE and RE regions within the first 30 minutes post ablation. These changes allow the prediction of the areas evolving towards a durable lesion from those that will recover. After the first 30 min, changes detected in the electrograms are less obvious.

Additionally, this study demonstrates clear differences in lesion morphology between PFA and RFA applied with a focal monopolar catheter epicardially. Considerably more elongated lesions were obtained in PFA suggesting advantages for deep targets compared to RFA.

Our findings establish the foundations for the interpretation of the surrounding PFA lesion electrograms and would contribute to future developments in the electroanatomical mapping systems and iEGM signal analysis algorithms to improve the predictive value of post-ablation maps after PFA treatments. Future studies may explore the correlation between signal changes and lesion depth.

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Disclosures

Dr. García-Sánchez is a consultant for Argá Medtech SA and Medlumics SL. Dr. Guerra has served as consultant for Biosense Webster, Boston Scientific and Abbott, received speaker fees from Boston Scientific and Abbott, and received a research grant from Abbott and Medtronic. Dr Ivorra is a consultant for Argá Medtech SA and Medlumics SL.

Supplemental Material

List of Supplemental Materials:

- Supplemental Information
- Supplementary Table I
- Supplemental Figures I-V
- Supplementary Videos V1-V2
- References: 24

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Table 1 title:

Values of electrogram parameters in the different rings at different time points

Table 1 legend:

Values of the different parameters recorded at baseline and 1 min, 5 min, 15 min, 30 min and 60 min post PFA application. p-values report the significance of differences between different rings.

			Baseline	1 min	5 min	15 min	30 min	60 min
ST (mV)	1000 V	Lesion center	0.0 ± 0.3	5.8 ± 1.8	4.3 ± 1.4	2.5 ± 1.0	1.3 ± 0.4	0.5 ± 0.2
		Lesion border	0.0 ± 0.2	4.2 ± 1.7	2.9 ± 1.2	1.6 ± 0.9	0.8 ± 0.4	0.3 ± 0.2
		Lesion periphery	0.0 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 3.2	2.5 ± 1.7	1.4 ± 1.1	0.6 ± 0.4	0.2 ± 0.2
		p-value center vs. periphery	0.35	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
		p-value center vs. border	0.19	0.88	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
		p-value border vs. periphery	0.12	0.05	0.03	0.04	<0.01	<0.01
	2000 V	Lesion center	0.0 ± 0.3	8.6 ± 2.4	6.0 ± 1.5	4.1 ± 1.8	2.4 ± 1.2	0.8 ± 0.6
		Lesion border	0.1 ± 0.2	6.9 ± 2.8	4.6 ± 1.7	2.5 ± 1.6	1.4 ± 1.0	0.4 ± 0.4
		Lesion periphery	0.1 ± 0.3	5.9 ± 2.4	3.9 ± 1.5	1.3 ± 0.8	0.7 ± 0.6	0.3 ± 0.3
		p-value center vs. periphery	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
		p-value center vs. border	0.05	0.14	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
		p-value border vs. periphery	0.31	0.27	0.09	<0.01	0.03	0.13
RS (mV)	1000 V	Lesion center	6.0 ± 3.3	0.6 ± 0.5	1.1 ± 0.9	1.4 ± 0.7	2.1 ± 0.8	2.6 ± 0.7
		Lesion border	5.5 ± 2.8	1.2 ± 1.0	2.1 ± 1.2	2.1 ± 1.1	2.7 ± 1.0	2.9 ± 0.9
		Lesion periphery	5.7 ± 2.8	1.7 ± 1.0	2.8 ± 1.2	2.6 ± 1.0	3.0 ± 1.0	3.1 ± 0.9
		p-value center vs. periphery	0.80	0.04	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
		p-value center vs. border	0.81	0.76	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.048
		p-value border vs. periphery	0.76	0.02	<0.01	0.01	0.15	0.44
	2000 V	Lesion center	6.7 ± 1.9	0.1 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.5	0.9 ± 0.9	2.1 ± 1.4	3.4 ± 1.5
		Lesion border	5.5 ± 2.3	0.1 ± 0.1	2.3 ± 1.2	2.3 ± 1.3	3.2 ± 1.5	3.9 ± 1.4
		Lesion periphery	5.4 ± 2.8	0.2 ± 1.0	3.1 ± 1.2	3.7 ± 1.0	3.9 ± 1.0	4.3 ± 0.9
		p-value center vs. periphery	0.20	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
		p-value center vs. border	0.08	0.25	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.15
		p-value border vs. periphery	0.9	0.06	0.35	0.02	0.28	0.29
dV/dt _{max} (mV/s)	1000 V	Lesion center	2938 ± 2216	433 ± 259	604 ± 368	622 ± 274	817 ± 338	843 ± 333
		Lesion border	2666 ± 2354	402 ± 235	820 ± 484	758 ± 355	840 ± 318	822 ± 321
		Lesion periphery	3413 ± 2360	849 ± 591	1394 ± 867	1179 ± 725	1325 ± 817	1329 ± 825
		p-value center vs. periphery	0.20	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
		p-value center vs. border	0.74	0.63	0.075	0.12	0.61	0.93
		p-value border vs. periphery	0.65	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
	2000 V	Lesion center	2962 ± 1864	58 ± 74	310 ± 138	271 ± 178	490 ± 315	713 ± 321
		Lesion border	2644 ± 2085	74 ± 77	783 ± 820	712 ± 583	825 ± 537	938 ± 384
		Lesion periphery	2208 ± 1885	137 ± 131	1037 ± 1486	1083 ± 1165	988 ± 819	1029 ± 613
		p-value center vs. periphery	0.20	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.02	0.03
		p-value center vs. border	0.51	0.58	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.036
		p-value border vs. periphery	0.62	0.12	0.92	0.13	0.30	0.45

Table 2 title:

Cutoffs values between irreversible and reversible electroporation areas.

Table 2 legend:

Table 2 displays the cutoff values between irreversible and reversible electroporation areas of the different parameters recorded at baseline and 5 min, 10min, 15min and 30 min post PFA at 1000V and 2000V. For RS amplitude and $|dV/dt|_{max}$, tissue displaying a reduction in these parameters greater than the cutoff values would correspond to IRE. For ST-segment elevation, tissue displaying a recovery lower than the cutoffs would correspond to IRE. p-values report the significance of differences of IRE (border) vs. RE (periphery) rings. ns (non-significant); *($p < 0.05$); ** ($p < 0.01$).

		5min	10min	15min	30 min
$dV/dt _{max}$ (% reduction vs. baseline)	1000 V	↓69.2 (**)	↓70.8 (**)	↓71.6 (**)	↓68.5 (**)
	2000 V	↓70.4 (ns)	↓70.3 (ns)	↓73.1 (ns)	↓68.8 (ns)
RS (% reduction vs. baseline)	1000 V	↓61.8 (**)	↓61.8 (**)	↓61.8 (**)	↓50.9 (ns)
	2000 V	↓58.2 (ns)	↓54.5 (ns)	↓58.2 (*)	↓41.8 (ns)
ST-segment elevation (% recovery from max elevation)	1000 V	↑31.0 (*)	↑50.0 (*)	↑61.9 (*)	↑81.0 (**)
	2000 V	↑33.3 (ns)	↑56.5 (*)	↑63.8 (**)	↑79.7 (*)

Figures, Figure legends and Figure Titles

Figure 1 title: Experimental setup

Figure 1. a) Schematic representation of the experimental setup for electrogram recording and ablation. The 3D-printed positioning frame (yellow) is sutured on the epicardial surface. In recording mode, the high-density microelectrodes matrix is placed on the epicardial surface; in the ablation mode, a plastic holder ensures that the ablation electrode is placed at the position corresponding to the center of the matrix. b) Illustrative electric field distribution computed with COMSOL Multiphysics for PFA at 1000V. The right panel (top view) displays an overlay of the electric field distribution at the epicardial surface and the position of the microelectrodes (small black squares). The different color circles correspond to the rings (groups of microelectrodes) that were analyzed. c) Electric field magnitude in a radial line from the center of the setup. Vertical color lines correspond to the position of the circles according to b).

Figure 2 title: Lesion dimensions and ring analysis correspondence

Figure 2. a) Example photographs of TTC staining results of one lesion at 1000 V (up) and at 2000 V (down) in the left ventricle. b) Quantification of lesion dimensions for PFA at 1000 V and 2000 V after TTC staining. Depth (D) and width (W) are reported as mean \pm SD (n=5). *p<0.05. c) Schematic top view of the setup: superposition of mean lesion diameter (red circle (1000 V) and blue circle (2000 V)) extracted from the TTC stained tissue samples, the electrode matrix and the rings used in the analysis. The correlation between lesion width (or lesion diameter) and the assigned rings for the analysis is shown (\emptyset is the diameter of each ring).

Figure 3 title: Electrogram changes in the left ventricle for 1000 V

Figure 3. a) Representative example of electrogram morphology in the whole recording matrix at baseline and different time points after PFA application at 1000 V. Color circles represent the position of the rings that were subsequently analyzed (center, border and periphery). Magnification corresponds to electrograms in a row at 5 min post PFA. b) Dynamic evolution of the mean values per region of the different parameters analyzed: ST-segment elevation (mV), RS amplitude (mV) and $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ (mV/s). Time=0 corresponds to baseline (pre-PFA); Time=1 min corresponds to post PFA. Values are reported as mean and SD (vertical lines). c) Representative example at 1000 V of contour color maps corresponding to the values of the three parameters analyzed in the whole matrix at different time points. The rings included in the color maps at 10 min correspond to areas where electrograms are analyzed (center, border and periphery).

Figure 4 title: Electrogram changes in the left ventricle for 2000 V

Figure 4. a) Representative example of electrogram morphology in the whole recording matrix at baseline and different time points after PFA application at 2000 V. Color circles represent the position of the rings that were subsequently analyzed (center, border and periphery). b) Dynamic evolution of the mean values per region of the different parameters analyzed: ST-segment elevation (mV), RS amplitude (mV) and $|(dV/dt)|_{\max}$ (mV/s). Time=0 corresponds to baseline (pre-PFA); Time=1 min corresponds to post PFA. Values are reported as mean and SD (vertical lines). c) Representative example at 2000 V of contour color maps corresponding to the values of the three parameters analyzed in the whole matrix at different time points. The rings included in the color maps at 10 min correspond to areas where electrograms are analyzed (center, border and periphery).

Figure 5 title: Comparison between Radiofrequency and Pulsed Field Ablation

Figure 5. a) Quantification of lesion dimensions (width and depth) for radiofrequency ablation (RF) at 30 W for 30 s after TTC staining. Data for Pulsed Field Ablation (PFA) at 2000 V is included for comparison. Values are reported as mean \pm SD (n=5). n.s (non-significant), *p<0.05. b) Dynamic evolution of the mean values per region of the different parameters analyzed corresponding to RF ablation: ST-segment elevation (mV), RS amplitude (mV) and $|dV/dt|_{\max}$ (mV/s). Time=0 corresponds to baseline (pre-PFA); Time=1 min corresponds to post PFA. Values are reported as mean and SD (vertical lines).

